

D6.1 - Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

prepared for

WP6.1 – Strategy for dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

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Approved by: Barbara Imhof

Liquifer

Work Package Leader

Approved by: Paul Zabel

DLR

Project Leader

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
1	DLR	
2	LSG	M. Brandić Lipińska, B. Imhof
3	TUBS	
4	SW	
5	PWR	
6	TAS	

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
LUWEX	Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies		
AI	Artificial Intelligence		
ISRU	In-Situ Resource Utilisation		

1 Plan of Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Activities

The LUWEX project, funded under the EU's Horizon Europe framework programme and led by the German Aerospace Centre (DLR), focused on the development of technologies for extracting purified water from lunar rock. The project's primary goal was to develop, integrate, and validate lunar water extraction and purification technologies to enable the production of in-situ propellants and consumables for future space exploration missions. This effort was essential for sustainable space exploration, as utilizing water resources directly from the Moon can significantly reduce the reliance on Earth-based supplies, crucial for long-term missions on the Moon, Mars, and beyond.

The LUWEX project aimed to achieve several key objectives, including the development of a water extraction, purification, and quality monitoring process chain for raw water, the design and manufacture of an integrated validation test setup, and the validation of these technologies in laboratory environments. Furthermore, it sought to advance Europe's leadership in space exploration by fostering interdisciplinary collaboration across academia, industry, and institutional research. These efforts positioned the European space sector to become a leading actor in water extraction and purification technologies, which are crucial for future lunar missions and the sustainable use of lunar resources.

The dissemination and exploitation of the LUWEX project's findings played a critical role in ensuring its success and long-lasting impact. Activities within Work Package 6 were dedicated to communicating the results of the project to a wide range of stakeholders, including the scientific community, industry professionals, policymakers, and the general public. This outreach was carried out through a variety of means, such as scientific publications, conference presentations, media coverage, and educational tools aimed at students. Additionally, the LUWEX team used diverse channels and formats, including text, video, and photos, to ensure the widest possible reach.

Dissemination efforts were started early in the project with the development of a strategic plan [see Figure 1]. A dedicated project website was launched, which served as a hub for all major achievements and provided detailed information on the project's progress. This included milestone results, photos, videos, podcasts, and interviews, all aimed at fostering a wider understanding of the project's significance. The website, along with the project flyer and summary brochure, became key tools for spreading the project's findings both during and after its completion. These materials, alongside a project video, were made available online and were used in various outreach activities, including trade fairs, exhibitions, and academic conferences.

One of the key goals of the dissemination activities was to ensure that LUWEX's findings had a lasting impact on both the scientific community and the wider public. This was achieved by creating a network of interested parties, including researchers, industry professionals, and space exploration enthusiasts. Special attention was given to maintaining an online presence through social media and professional networking sites to reach a broad audience and stimulate ongoing interest in the project's results.

The LUWEX project's dissemination activities not only aimed to share the project's advancements but also to foster collaboration and promote Europe's leading role in the space exploration sector. By ensuring wide distribution of its results and engaging with various audiences, LUWEX contributed significantly to advancing knowledge in the field of lunar water extraction and purification, helping to pave the way for future space missions and the sustainable use of extraterrestrial resources.

Figure 1. Plan for dissemination and exploitation, including communication activities.

1.1 Project’s visual identification

Developing a clear project identity was crucial for creating a product that was both recognizable and approachable to various stakeholders. The goals of the project identity were to communicate the project’s aims and accomplishments clearly. Continuous input from project partners on milestone developments, communicated in a timely manner, aimed to foster scientific dialogue and ensure maximum visibility.

The project identity was achieved alongside the development of the project website. A key design driver was to create a visually appealing webpage that captured the essence of the LUWEX project in a light, approachable, and accessible manner, while also providing concrete information about the project’s goals, aims, objectives, expected outcomes, and impact. Presenting the project from these dual perspectives was conceptualized to ensure broad accessibility for all stakeholders.

The colour scheme, logo, diagrams, and other visual elements were consistently applied, creating a cohesive visual identity for the project.

1.1.1 Logo

Figure 2 shows the project’s logo. The graphic represents the lunar surface, and a water droplet, highlighting the project main goal - integration and validation of lunar water extraction and purification technologies.

Figure 2. Project logo

1.1.2 Graphics

Using MidJourney, an artificial intelligence (AI) program that generates images from textual descriptions, alongside Photoshop, the LUWEX team created original visuals designed to communicate the project’s idea in a more artistic and abstract manner [see Figure 3].

Figure 3. AI generated and photoshopped visuals presenting LUWEX idea.

1.2 Project documentation and publications

The LUWEX consortium aligned with the European Commission’s vision on open science and implemented the mandatory practices, such as:

- Open access to scientific publications,
- Responsible management of research data in line with the FAIR principles, including a data management plan and open access to research data,
- Information about the research outputs, tools, instruments needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications or to validate research data,
- Digital or physical access to the results needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications, unless exceptions apply,

- Immediate open access to all research outputs in cases of public emergency, if requested by the granting authority.

Open access to scientific publications accelerated the research and discovery process, leading to increased returns on investments provided by the European Commission and avoiding the duplication of research efforts. The project partners followed the recommendations outlined in the annotated model grant agreement and established a clear framework for open access to scientific publications within the LUXWEX grant agreement.

LUXWEX partners not only provided open access to peer-reviewed publications but also made project deliverables, data sets, and detailed experiment descriptions available. Flyers, brochures, and papers were also accessible on the LUXWEX website.

1.2.1 Scientific publications

For the dissemination of the project, a considerable number of scientific publications was published based on the scientific and technology validation results.

Papers were regularly prepared by individual consortium members and served as important criteria for conferences. The goal was to make the LUXWEX project accessible to a wide range of target groups, including universities, industries, and the European Space Agency (ESA).

All consortium partners published key technical and scientific results at international conferences, workshops, and in journals. Publications were reviewed and authorized by the Management Board after considering the impact on the established IPR. The Scientific Advisory Board supported the promotion and publication activities. Main targets included specialized journals and magazines in aerospace engineering, space resources, and general space journals and magazines.

All scientific publications related to LUXWEX were open access (if possible) and made available through the website and social media networks.

2 D6.2 Website

A dedicated website (www.luwex.space) was maintained throughout the project duration by LSG, with active contributions from all partners. The project website was well-designed, interactive, and user-friendly (front-end). It was created to incorporate dynamic text that enabled easy access to the site and its contents from various-sized electronic devices.

The website served as a platform for posting relevant news about and associated with the LUXWEX project and, most importantly, it provided information on the project's development. It featured a dynamic 'gallery space' that showcased milestone results, photos, video animation clips, podcasts, and personnel interviews. The website also included a link to the repository storing open-access, peer-reviewed publications (conference proceedings, journal papers, etc.).

2.1 Website components

2.1.1 Homepage

The homepage [see Figure 4] which served as the landing site for first-time visitors, featured the main graphic, presenting the artistic idea of the project, alongside the project name. For the easy navigation on the website, at the top of the homepage (and repeated at every other page) there is a menu bar with seven menu items: NEWS, PROJECT, GALLERIES, PODCASTS, PUBLICATIONS, PARTNERS, and CONTACT.

The main visual captured the project's essence, showcasing a collage of water bubbles and an astronaut sitting on the Moon, drinking water, and looking at the lunar surface.

The main visual and project name were followed by three "cards" for different website sections—news, podcasts, and galleries—along with direct links to the most recent news, podcast, and gallery. These "cards" stood out as their contents changed frequently, providing returning visitors with signs of updates and new information.

The cards are followed by a short project description exemplifying the project main idea, presenting the consortium partners, and referring to the EU Framework programme. At the footer of the homepage, a logo is featured for each consortium member with a link to their respective websites opening in a new tab. Information regarding project funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme is included, as well as the grant agreement number [see Figure 5].

Figure 4. A screenshot of the LUXEW website – landing page (www.luwx.space).

WATER ON THE MOON

L UWEX is a project funded under the EU's Horizon Europe framework programme under the lead of the German Aerospace Centre, DLR. L UWEX stands for Lunar Water Extraction. It is focussed on developing technologies to obtain purified water from moon rock.

L UWEX CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Germany / LIQUIFER Systems Group, Austria / Technische Universität Braunschweig, Germany / Scanway sp. z o.o., Poland / Wrocław University for Science and Technology, Poland / Thales Alenia Space, Italy

Figure 5. LUWEX landing page bottom with partners and reference to EU project grant.

2.1.2 News

The News section of the website [see Figure 6] was regularly updated with the latest updates from the LUWEX team members. It showcased key events such as meetings, workshops (including Concurrent Engineering Workshops), conferences, symposia, and other significant project developments. This section provided up-to-date news flashes on the exciting advancements within the project, covering participation in conferences, classroom engagements, partner meetings, and scientific discoveries. Its aim was to highlight the dynamic efforts of the LUWEX project, illustrating not only the progress in scientific advancements but also the broader applications that could benefit society at large.

FEBRUARY 12, 2023

Concurrent Engineering (CE) Workshop 1

The LUWEX team met in January 2023 to establish the validation test setup design using the Concurrent Engineering (CE) process. It is a system approach with a focus on optimizing engineering design cycles. It replaces the traditional hierarchical, sequential design-flow by integrating multidisciplinary teams that work collectively and in parallel; often in intense, short studies. [...]

[Detailed Information](#)

NOVEMBER 15, 2022

WATER ON THE MOON

A European science team is advancing the development of water extraction from lunar regolith (surface material).

LEADING IDEA

The development, integration and validation of lunar water extraction and purification technologies for lunar propellant and consumables production is a key requirement for future space exploration.

LUWEX, a project funded under the EU's Horizon Europe framework programme has started with a kick-off meeting under the lead of the German Aerospace Centre, DLR. LUWEX stands for Lunar Water Extraction and the project is focused on developing technologies to obtain purified water from moon rock.

Water is the driving force of all nature. Leonardo da Vinci said. Water is life for the most versatile and most needed resource in human space exploration. It is the key commodity to life support systems as well as for organic chemical and drug production.

Moon rocks are transported in the amount of mass initially placed in orbit. As we advance deeper into space, the cost to support exploration missions with Earth-based resources increases with distance. More than 7.5 kg of propellant and vehicle mass are required to deliver each kilogram of payload to the lunar surface. The utilization of available local resources is key to a sustainable human presence on the moon or Mars and beyond. Indicators to the availability of local raw water for transport to the lunar and Martian soil provide the motivation and substantial interest in viable technical solutions for finding, extracting, purifying and utilizing in-situ water. Previous research activities regarding lunar water extraction were mostly performed as theoretical system studies, complemented by a few small-scale experiments.

Press release 1

The interdisciplinary LUWEX team coming from Germany, Austria, Poland and Italy is designing and testing a novel water extractor that will be able to process several kilograms of lunar regolith containing enough water ice to support a purification process downstream. The terrestrial demonstration system will operate under a similar low pressure and low temperature environment [...]

[Detailed Information](#)

NOVEMBER 4, 2022

Kick-Off Meeting

The virtual Kick-Off meeting with all LUWEX partners took place 3 November 2022. The first part was open to the public.

[Detailed Information](#)

Figure 6. LUWEX website news section

2.1.3 Project

The project was described on a single page (with no extra sub-pages to click on) and was divided into Context, Vision/Approach, and Objectives, with listed expected outcomes and impact. In the project description, we ensured that the language used was less technical and specialized, making it accessible to a wider audience. We created diagrammatic graphics to present the project idea [see Figure 7] and the expected outcomes and impact [see Figure 8]. The most important and easy-to-grasp phrases were highlighted in bold to increase their visibility and readability.

Figure 7. Diagrams explaining LUWEX main concept

Figure 8. Diagrams presenting the timeline of research and innovation of leading-edge ISRU technologies, excellent science for space exploration of the Moon, and supporting the development of the European space sector.

2.1.4 Galleries

The Galleries section supplemented the News section and showcased images from team meetings, workshops, conferences, and exhibitions. It provided an up-to-date visual sneak peek into all activities associated with project development, including progression meetings, workshops, participation in conferences, classroom engagements, project partner meetings, and cutting-edge scientific discoveries. The section aimed to illustrate, through its collection of various events and achievements, the dynamic efforts the project made, not only in scientific advancement but also in applications that could benefit society at large.

2.1.5 Podcasts

Podcast section provided a quick access to the LUXWEX WATER BEYOND EARTH podcast [see Section 5].

2.1.6 Publications

The Publications section was regularly updated with publications from the LUXWEX team, such as exhibition and conference posters, project flyers, and press releases. It was also a space where, in the future, conference and journal papers would be published.

2.1.7 Partners

The LUXWEX project was comprised of 6 international partners, including universities, research institutions, and companies. On this website sub-page, the expertise of each partner was described, as well as the tasks they will accomplish in the LUXWEX project.

2.1.8 Contact

Contact information including contact person, address, email address and telephone number for each consortium partner is given.

2.2 Social media

A dedicated LinkedIn account was created for the project [see Figure 9].

Major project highlights, as well as general descriptions, were shared via the website and also posted on LinkedIn and Instagram through private consortium partners' profiles. Videos, including the project video and videocast mini-series, were uploaded to YouTube and Vimeo as they were created.

Researchers from the consortium used their profiles on platforms such as ResearchGate, Academia.edu, and others to disseminate project results and promote the project.

Figure 9. Screenshot of a LUWEX LinkedIn page.

3 D6.3: Project flyer

Early in the project, we prepared a project flyer as a promotional document to disseminate information about LUWEX to a wide audience. The purpose of the flyer was to raise awareness about the project and its objectives, highlight the main features and benefits, and encourage people to get involved or support the project in some way.

One side of the flyer presented key project information [see Figure 10] while the other side featured a more graphical design that could be turned into a small poster [see Figure 11]. Including a visual graphic with partner logos on the reverse side helped to make the flyer more engaging and memorable, making it easier for people to share and discuss.

The project flyer was printed and distributed as a giveaway at conferences or during personal encounters. It was also published on the project website as a pdf available for download.

Figure 10. The internal side of the project flyer

Figure 11. The visual side of the project flyer

4 Press Releases

Throughout the project, three press releases were issued [see Figure 12, Figure 13, and Figure 14].

These releases were made available on the LUWEX website and translated by project partners into their respective languages for distribution through their networks, ensuring broad outreach to diverse audiences.

The press releases were designed to be visually attractive and generally understandable, offering updates on project outcomes and events such as workshops and conferences. They described the objectives and approaches of the LUWEX project, highlighting milestones and listing contact information, as well as providing general information about the consortium and the funding agency. The releases also served as PR for the various agencies and were sent to respective press agencies, as well as to National and European press distributions.

Press Release 1 was completed in November 2022 and focused on the project's goals and the general topics to be explored by the LUWEX team. Press Release 2 was published at the start of the experiment campaign, while Press Release 3 highlighted the outcomes of the project and campaign.

4.1 D6.4: Press Release 1

WATER ON THE MOON

A European science team is advancing the development of water extraction from lunar regolith (surface material).

LEADING IDEA

The development, integration and validation of lunar water extraction and purification technologies for in-situ propellant and consumables production is a key requirement for future space exploration.

Distribution of lunar water ice

LUWEX, a project funded under the EU's Horizon Europe framework programme has started with a kick-off meeting under the lead of the German Aerospace Centre, DLR. LUWEX stands for Lunar Water Extraction and the project is focussed on developing technologies to obtain purified water from moon rock.

Water is the driving force of all nature, Leonardo da Vinci said. Water is by far the most versatile and most needed resource for human space exploration. It is the key commodity in life support systems as well as for cryogenic chemical rocket propellants.

Mission costs are proportional to the amount of mass initially placed in orbit. As we advance deeper into space, the cost to support exploration missions with Earth-based resources increases with distances. More than 7.5 kg of propellant and vehicle mass are required to deliver each kilogram of payload to the lunar surface. The utilisation of available local resources is key to a sustainable human presence on the moon or Mars and beyond. Indications for the availability of local raw water ice trapped in the lunar and Martian soil provide the motivation and substantial interest in viable technical solutions for finding, extracting, purifying and utilizing in situ-water. Previous research activities regarding lunar water extraction were mostly performed as theoretical system studies, complemented by a few small-scale experiments.

The interdisciplinary LUWEX team coming from Germany, Austria, Poland and Italy is designing and testing a novel water extractor that will be able to process several kilograms of lunar regolith containing enough water ice to support a purification process downstream. The terrestrial demonstration system will operate under a similar low pressure and low temperature environment as on the moon.

To test the system in the laboratory, a mix from water ice particles and lunar regolith simulant will substitute for real lunar sand as is expected to be found in some craters at the lunar south polar region. By applying heat, the vaporizing water is extracted and collected. After liquefaction, the raw water is put through a purification process. The purified water is then ready for use in the form of propellant, for energy storage and for life support, or for a glass of Adam's ale from the moon.

PARTICIPANT ORGANISATIONS

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Germany
 LIQUIFER Systems Group, Austria
 Technische Universität Braunschweig, Germany
 Scanway sp. z o. o., Poland
 Wrocław University for Science and Technology, Poland
 Thales Alenia Space, Italy

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Figure 12. Press Release 1.

4.2 D6.5: Press Release 2

European project tests groundbreaking water extraction from lunar dust for the first time.

29 April 2024

LEADING THE WAY

European Union-backed project LUWEX develops a pioneering system that enables the extraction of water from lunar regolith, a crucial step in advancing space exploration and sustaining human presence on the Moon.

Under the lead of the German Aerospace Center Bremen, LUWEX has engineered a comprehensive process that not only extracts water from icy regolith but also purifies it to supply rocket fuel and drinking water for astronauts stationed on the lunar surface.

These groundbreaking tests will unfold at the TU Braunschweig, specifically at the Institute of Geophysics and Extraterrestrial Physics. Central to these tests is a meticulously implemented laboratory setup that mirrors the conditions found in the shadowed regions of the moon's south pole using icy lunar regolith simulant. This material is not real lunar regolith but synthesized on earth and resembles lunar dust to a very high degree.

The laboratory setup includes both components inside a vacuum chamber as well as components placed outside, depending on their expected operational environment.

- Unit for moon-like regolith:** the experiment uses regolith simulant with a 5% ice content.
- Ice and Regolith Separation Crucible:** water ice is separated from regolith through stirring and heating, water ice is converted into water vapour and can escape from the regolith.
- Dry Regolith Removal:** the remaining regolith without the ice is being removed and stored for further resource usage such as mineral extraction or for building habitats.
- Cold Trap:** the water vapour is cooled and frozen again into water ice to capture it.
- Liquidation:** water ice is being heated up again to provide liquid water.

The components outside the vacuum chamber include:

- Water purification outside the vacuum chamber: water is being cleaned and monitored so it is safe to drink.

What was once a conceptual idea has now been transformed into a fully operational demonstrator system, thanks to the collaborative efforts of six European partners from Germany, Italy, Poland, and Austria.

SUMMARY

LUWEX, short for Validation of Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies for In-Situ Propellant and Consumables Production, represents a significant milestone in space exploration. Funded under the EU's Horizon Europe framework program and led by the German Aerospace Center, Bremen this initiative pioneers the whole process chain to extract water from lunar regolith simulant and thus revolutionizes our understanding of lunar resource utilization.

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PARTICIPANT ORGANISATIONS AND CONTACTS

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Germany

- Dr. Paul Zabel, paul.zabel@dlr.de, +49421244201273
- Luca Kiewiet, luca.kiewiet@dlr.de

Technische Universität Braunschweig, Germany

- Christopher Kreuzig, c.kreuzig@tu-braunschweig.de, +495313915198
- Johanna Nonia Brecher, j.brecher@tu-braunschweig.de, +495313915198
- Gerwin Meier, gerwin.meier@tu-braunschweig.de, +495313915198
- Christian Schuckart, c.schuckart@tu-braunschweig.de, +495311398516
- Prof. Jürgen Blum, j.blum@tu-braunschweig.de, +495313915217

LIQUIFER Systems Group, Austria

- Dr. Barbara Imhof, barbara.imhof@liquifer.com, +43121885-05

Thales Alenia Space, Italy

- Cinzia Marcanio, cinzia.marcanio@thalesaleniaspace.com

Wroclaw University for Science and Technology, Poland

- Karol Lesiuk, karol.lesiuk@pwr.edu.pl, +48 668 378 732

Scanway sp. z o. o., Poland

- Szymon Krawczuk, s.krawczuk@scanway.pl, +48 71 733 62 64
- Mikołaj Podgórski, m.podgorski@scanway.pl

Figure 13. Press Release 2.

4.3 D6.6: Press Release 3

Water from Moon Dust

LUWEX SUCCESSFULLY DEMONSTRATES TECHNOLOGIES FOR EXTRACTING WATER FROM LUNAR REGOLITH

7 January 2025

Image: LUWEX consortium

As part of the project LUWEX (Validation of Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies for In-Situ Propellant and Consumables Production), an international team of researchers developed and successfully demonstrated technologies for extracting water from lunar regolith in laboratory conditions, showing how ice could be extracted from simulated lunar regolith. The extracted and purified water holds the potential for use as drinking water, oxygen production, or cryogenic rocket propellant in space—a critical step in supporting sustainable exploration of the solar system.

Led by the German Aerospace Center (DLR) in Bremen, the LUWEX research project developed and tested a water extraction process in large-scale experiments conducted at TU Braunschweig over several months. Each trial aimed to produce at least half a litre of water, a goal that was consistently achieved and even exceeded.

SIMULATING LUNAR CONDITIONS IN THE LAB

The LUWEX process was validated through experiments at TU Braunschweig's CoPhyLab (Comet Physics Laboratory), a unique facility designed to replicate lunar surface conditions. During the trials, nearly 65% of the water in the simulated regolith was successfully extracted and purified. Over the course of the experiments, more than three litres of potable water were produced. The laboratory setup included a thermal vacuum chamber capable of simulating temperatures as low as -170°C under vacuum conditions. This facility, originally developed for comet research, enabled researchers to test extraction techniques at a realistic scale. Comprehensive monitoring was achieved using 14 integrated measurement systems, ensuring precise validation of the technology.

Left: Polluted raw water directly after the water extraction and capturing process. Right: Clean water as a result after purifying the raw water. Image: LUWEX consortium

COLLABORATIVE INTERNATIONAL EFFORT

The LUWEX project brought together an interdisciplinary team from Germany, Austria, Poland, and Italy. Key participants included TU Braunschweig, DLR, LIQUIFER Systems Group, Thales Alenia Space, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, and SCANWAY SPACE. Each partner contributed critical subsystems or infrastructure, reflecting the project's collaborative nature.

Some of the LUWEX team members. Image: LUWEX consortium

SUMMARY

PRODUCING ICE-BEARING LUNAR REGOLITH IN THE LAB

To simulate lunar regolith containing ice, scientists created a dust-ice mixture by combining synthetic lunar regolith with ice particles.

The ice was produced by flash-freezing fine water droplets in liquid nitrogen, creating spherical particles with an average radius of 2.4 micrometres—approximately one-twentieth the thickness of a human hair.

EXTRACTING AND PURIFYING WATER

The lunar ice simulant was placed in the water extraction system developed by DLR, located within the thermal vacuum chamber, allowing it to be tested under lunar-like conditions. Up to 15 kilograms of the simulant were placed in a pre-cooled container inside the vacuum chamber. The atmosphere was evacuated, and the simulant was heated and stirred to ensure even heat distribution. Under these conditions, the ice sublimated directly into water vapour, which was captured on copper tubes cooled to -150°C. The vapour re-condensed into ice, which was later liquefied for collection and purification.

Thales Alenia Space and Wrocław University of Science and Technology were responsible for purifying the extracted water, ensuring its quality met stringent requirements for human use and rocket propellant production. Researchers optimised parameters such as temperature and stirring speed to maximise water yield while minimising energy consumption.

Ice machine for producing granular water ice. In the background, the piezo element is visible. In the foreground, water mist. Image: LUWEX consortium

The LUWEX project, short for Validation of Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies for In-Situ Propellant and Consumables Production, funded by the EU's Horizon Europe framework program, marks a significant milestone in lunar resource utilisation. By successfully developing and demonstrating technologies to extract and purify water from lunar regolith simulants, the project has laid the groundwork for sustainable space exploration and paved the way for future in-situ resource utilisation initiatives.

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Space Science and Exploration Technologies

PARTICIPANT ORGANISATIONS AND CONTACTS

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Germany

- Dr. Paul Zabel, paul.zabel@dlr.de, +49421244201273
- Luca Kiewiet, luca.kiewiet@dlr.de

Technische Universität Braunschweig, Germany

- Christopher Kreuzig, c.kreuzig@tu-braunschweig.de, +495313915198
- Johanna Noria Brecher, j.brecher@tu-braunschweig.de, +495313915198
- Gerwin Meier, gerwin.meier@tu-braunschweig.de, +495313915198
- Christian Schuckart, c.schuckart@tu-braunschweig.de, +495311398516
- Prof. Jürgen Blum, j.blum@tu-braunschweig.de, +495313915217

LIQUIFER Systems Group, Austria

- Dr. Barbara Imhof, barbara.imhof@liquifer.com, +43121885-05

Thales Alenia Space, Italy

- Cinzia Marcanio, cinzia.marcanio@thalesaleniaspace.com

Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland

- Karol Leluk, karol.leluk@pwr.edu.pl, +48 668 378 732

Scanway S.A., Poland

- Szymon Krawczuk, s.krawczuk@scanway.pl, +48 71 733 62 64
- Mikolaj Podgorski, m.podgorski@scanway.pl

Figure 14. Press Release 3.

5 D6.7: Podcast mini-series

As part of the LUWEX project's outreach efforts, we produced a podcast series titled *Water Beyond Earth* [see Figure 15]. The primary goal of the podcast was to engage the public and communicate the significance of the LUWEX project, its contributions to human space exploration, and broader topics related to space missions. Through discussions on key project developments and explorations of subjects such as water in space, in-situ resource utilisation, human space exploration, and related policies, legal considerations, and ethics, the podcast aimed to raise awareness and foster a deeper understanding of the challenges and innovations shaping the future of space exploration. Designed to be informative and comprehensive, the *Water Beyond Earth* podcast offered a unique exploration into the vast realm of space, providing a nuanced perspective on the limitless possibilities beyond our planet.

Figure 15. Podcast banner on Spotify

Podcast description from Spotify:

"In our podcast miniseries "Water Beyond Earth" we explore the captivating world of lunar water extraction and purification. Join us on an enthralling voyage into space exploration, as we focus on LUWEX, the groundbreaking endeavor for Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies. Throughout this podcast miniseries, we will explore the significance of water in space exploration and showcase cutting-edge technologies that enable this possibility. Together, we will immerse ourselves in the visionary goals of LUWEX and experience the fascinating process of harnessing water from the lunar regolith. Guest experts and scientists leading the way will guide us through innovative engineering marvels and the concept of in-situ resource utilization. "Water Beyond Earth" invites you to witness a world where cosmic dreams become reality, exploring the boundless potential that lies beyond Earth's boundaries. Get ready to embark on this extraordinary expedition with us! The podcast miniseries "Water Beyond Earth" is hosted by LUWEX, a research consortium that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2022 Research Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement no 10108193."

5.1 Podcast identity and representation

The podcast identity was consistent with the project identity. The podcast main graphic [see Figure 16] was created to align with the style of other graphics on the LUWEX website.

Figure 16: AI generated visuals for the LUWEX podcast

The podcast was published on Spotify [see Figure 17] and made available through the LUWEX project website [see Figure 18 and Figure 19] ensuring broad accessibility and engagement with a wide audience.

Podcast on Spotify:

<https://open.spotify.com/show/5c3MYH4HKzzqYpIKXEff36?si=18c20544d84c4ec6>

Podcast on LUWEX website:

<https://luwex.space/category/podcasts/>

Figure 17. Screenshot from the Spotify, when the Podcast page

[NEWS](#)
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[VIDEOS](#)
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MARCH 5, 2024

E06: Establishing a Moon Base

In this episode, we explore how humans might live and work on the Moon. With our guests, Dr. Jill Stuart, an expert in the politics, ethics, and law of outer space exploration and exploitation from the London School of Economics and Political Science, and Dr. Barbara Imhof, co-founder, Managing Partner, and co-owner of LIQUIFER, we [...]

[Detailed Information](#)
[Listen on Spotify](#)

FEBRUARY 23, 2024

E05: Water Purification

In this episode we delve into the crucial role of water in lunar and space exploration, discussing water processing and purification strategies. Our guests, Giorgio Boscheri, a Space Engineer from Thales Alenia Space Italia, and Anna Jurga and Karol Leluk, researchers from the Faculty of Environmental Engineering at Wrocław University of Science and Technology, bring [...]

[Detailed Information](#)
[Listen on Spotify](#)

Figure 18. Screenshot from the website, showcasing all the podcast episodes.

Figure 19. Screenshot from the website, showcasing specific podcast episode.

5.2 Podcast episodes

The podcast mini-series was divided into episodes focusing on specific topics.

E00: Trailer

Description: In our podcast miniseries “Water Beyond Earth”, hosted by LUWEX, we explore the captivating world of lunar water extraction and purification.

E01: Harnessing water on the Moon

Guests: Paul Zabel, DLR

Description:

Paul Zabel from DLR Institute of Space Systems, an aerospace engineer with a deep passion for science-fiction and space exploration, talk about the project LUWEX, and the importance and potential of water in lunar and space exploration.

E02: Water in the Universe

Guests: James Carpenter, ESA

Description: James Carpenter, a physicist specializing in space astrophysics and planetary science from the European Space Agency delves into the captivating topic of water within the universe.

E03: In-Situ Resource Utilization

Guests: Dr. Angel Abbud-Madrid, Colorado School of Mines

Description: Dr. Angel Abbud-Madrid, the Director of the Center for Space Resources at the Colorado School of Mines, as our guest, who is sharing insights on In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) in the realm of space exploration.

E04: Water Extraction

Guests: Luca Kiewiet, DLR; Christopher Kreuzig, Technische Universität Braunschweig

Short description: In this episode our focus will delve deeper into the technical aspects of the LUWEX project. Together with Luca Kiewiet, and Christopher Kreuzig we'll be exploring the process of extracting water from regolith.

Long description: In this episode our focus will delve deeper into the technical aspects of the LUWEX project. Together with Luca Kiewiet, a researcher from German Aerospace Center (DLR) in Bremen and Christopher Kreuzig, a researcher at the Technische Universität Braunschweig in the Institute of Geophysics and Extraterrestrial Physics, we'll be exploring the process of extracting water from regolith.

E05: Water Purification

Guests: Giorgio Boscheri, TAS; Anna Jurga, Karol Leluk, WUST

Short description: In this episode, we delve into the crucial role of water in lunar and space exploration, engaging in discussions about water processing and purification strategies with members of the LUWEX team: Giorgio Boscheri, Anna Jurga, and Karol Leluk.

Long description: In this episode we delve into the crucial role of water in lunar and space exploration, discussing water processing and purification strategies. Our guests, Giorgio Boscheri, a Space Engineer from Thales Alenia Space Italia, and Anna Jurga and Karol Leluk, researchers from the Faculty of Environmental Engineering at Wrocław University of Science and Technology, bring diverse perspectives to the discussion. We explore the significance of environmental engineering in space system design, emphasizing water's importance and the challenges of purifying lunar-extracted water. Topics include lunar water purification methods, tailored technologies for spacecraft environments, and the potential for in-situ agriculture on the Moon.

E06: Establishing a Moon Base

Guests: Dr. Jill Stuart, London School of Economics and Political Science; Dr. Barbara Imhof, LIQUIFER

Short description: Our guests, Dr. Jill Stuart, an expert in space politics, ethics, and law of outer space exploration and exploitation, and Dr. Barbara Imhof, co-founder, Managing Partner, and co-owner of LIQUIFER, discuss how humans might live and work on the Moon.

Long description: In this episode, we explore how humans might live and work on the Moon. With our guests, Dr. Jill Stuart, an expert in the politics, ethics, and law of outer space exploration and exploitation from the London School of Economics and Political Science, and Dr. Barbara Imhof, co-founder, Managing Partner, and co-owner of LIQUIFER, we explore the challenges of space architecture, delve into legal considerations, and discuss ethical dilemmas in human space exploration.

6 D6.8: Videocast mini-series

A videocast mini-series was hosted on the project website and published on the partners' YouTube channels, spotlighting the people behind the LUWEX project.

The mini-series was structured around concise interviews with team members [see Figure 20] who answered questions about the LUWEX project, offering insights into its objectives, challenges, and achievements. This format provided an engaging way to highlight the team's expertise and the innovative technologies developed during the project.

Figure 20: Screenshots from the video miniseries

6.1 Episodes

There are five episodes in the series:

1. About LUWEX.
An interview with Paul Zabel, LUWEX project coordinator.
<https://luwex.space/2023/11/08/about-luwex/>

2. Motivation for LUWEX

What the project team inspires about project LUWEX.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/07/motivation-for-luwex/>

3. About In-Situ-Resource-Utilisation ISRU

ISRU and how it is a sustainable practice.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/06/about-in-situ-resource-utilisation-isru/>

4. LUWEX challenges

What kind of challenges the LUWEX team faces in developing the project.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/05/luwex-challenges/>

5. LUWEX interviews on collaboration

Collaborative aspects of industry, academia and research institutions of project LUWEX.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/04/luwex-interviews-on-collaboration/>

6.2 Presentation

The videocast mini-series was hosted on the LUWEX website (see Figures 2 and 3) and published on the partners' YouTube channels (see Figure 4). The episodes were also shared via the LUWEX LinkedIn profile to maximise outreach and engagement.

Figure 21. Screenshot from the website, form the separate video page.

Figure 22. Screenshot from the website video page, showcasing all the videocast miniseries episodes.

7 D6.9: Summary Brochure

All project achievements were summarised in a printed and digital summary brochure, which is downloadable from the project website. The brochure serves as promotional material beyond the project’s lifetime and is designed for use in presentations or as standalone material to showcase the project’s outcomes and significance. Section 7.1 present brochure cover and section 7.2 the brochure content divided by its sections.

7.1 Brochure covers

Figure 23. Brochure covers with project name, funding information and partners’ logos.

7.2 Brochure sections

The LUWEX project is an initiative focused on developing and validating technologies for extracting, purifying and monitoring lunar water, and advancing In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) to support sustainable space exploration. Water is a vital resource for human space exploration, serving as a consumable for astronauts, radiation shielding, and, when split into hydrogen and oxygen, a crucial component of rocket fuel. By harnessing lunar water resources, LUWEX seeks to reduce reliance on Earth-bound supplies, paving the way for sustainable long-duration missions. The project employs an integrated test setup to simulate lunar conditions, using icy lunar dust simulants in a thermal-vacuum chamber to validate its process chain. This approach aims to elevate the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the system, supporting future European-led space exploration missions. Key project outcomes include the development of a lunar water extraction and purification system, validating ISRU technologies, and promoting interdisciplinary collaboration across academia, industry, and institutional research. By advancing Europe's capabilities in space exploration, LUWEX contributes to the global effort to make space missions more viable, affordable, and sustainable.

4

LUWEX

Validation of Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies for In-Situ Propellant and Consumables Production

Content

- Water in Space Exploration 7
- In-Site Resource Utilisation 8
- Water on the Moon 9
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- Harnessing Water on the Moon 13
- Project Objectives 14
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5

Figure 24. Brochure page 4-5.

7.2.1 Water in space exploration

Figure 25. Water in space exploration section.

7.2.2 Harnessing water on the Moon

Figure 26. Harnessing water on the Moon section.

7.2.3 System design and implementation

SIMULATING LUNAR CONDITIONS: THERMAL VACUUM CHAMBER (TVAC)

The Thermal Vacuum Chamber at Comet Physics Laboratory, TU Braunschweig, is a special-interest facility originally developed for comet research. It replicates lunar surface conditions, enabling experiments with dust ice mixtures at temperatures as low as -170°C under vacuum conditions.

The Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem were placed inside the Thermal Vacuum Chamber. To regulate lunar conditions, part of the TVAC is evacuated to 5×10^{-6} mbar using a turbomolecular pump and line pump, then cooled to 110K with dual liquid-nitrogen cooling systems.

The enable containing the ice/organism simulant is placed directly on the primary heating system, ensuring conduction-based cooling. This setup closely mimics the thermal conditions experienced by a satellite in direct contact with the lunar surface, making it an invaluable tool for simulating and studying water extraction processes on the Moon.

LUWEX-LSG-WP6.1-D6.1-Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities-v1.0

"We have a very deep vacuum and very cold temperature, exactly as it could be on the lunar surface. The combination of the experiment cycle and the relevant environment pushing the technology to its real limit."

Luca Reuter, German Aerospace Center

LUWEX-LSG-WP6.1-D6.1-Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities-v1.0

WATER EXTRACTION AND CAPTURING SUBSYSTEM (WECS)

The Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem (WECS) is designed to extract water vapor from the icy regolith simulant by sublimation and then supply it for storage and purification. The system achieves this through two key components: extraction subsystem and capturing subsystem.

Extraction Subsystem: The extraction subsystem sublimates the ice in the icy regolith simulant to generate water vapor. Due to the regolith's low thermal conductivity, a stirring mechanism was implemented to enhance heat distribution. Heating belts, installed at varying belt ratios to ensure uniform heating and prevent channel gaps in the simulant. This stirring also facilitates the escape of water vapor from dried-out regolith.

Capturing Subsystem: The capturing subsystem consists of a cold trap and a liquefaction chamber. The cold trap provides a surface cool enough for water vapor to freeze. Once sufficient ice accumulates, internal heaters are activated to sublimate the ice layer, causing it to drop into the liquefaction chamber. The liquefaction chamber is heated-off and heaters melt the collected ice into liquid water. The water is then transferred to Storage 1, located outside the vacuum chamber, for subsequent transport to the purification system.

The low thermal conductivity of lunar regolith poses challenges for heating and sublimation. To address this, a stirring mechanism was implemented. Heating rods were oriented to evenly distribute the heat and facilitate the release of water vapor.

LUWEX-LSG-WP6.1-D6.1-Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities-v1.0

The figure below presents a schematic overview of the entire Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem, as well as the boundaries of the vacuum chamber in which it is placed, and the tube used for filling the regolith in the icy regolith simulant. The different colored lines show the lines between the different subsystems and their boundaries.

The figure on the right shows how the assembled Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem looks inside the Thermal Vacuum Chamber after integration.

LUWEX-LSG-WP6.1-D6.1-Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities-v1.0

Water connection
TVAC
Filling tube
Slower
Emptying tube
Water vapour tube
Cold trap
Liquefaction chamber

LUWEX-LSG-WP6.1-D6.1-Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities-v1.0

WATER PURIFICATION SUBSYSTEM (WPS)

The Water Purification Subsystem is designed to treat the water from the Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem, which contains various contaminants, its goal is to meet the strict water quality requirements for water electrolysis, which are more demanding than those for potable water.

The purification methods were selected to minimize consumables, achieve high water recovery, and ensure scalability for lunar missions. Contaminants are categorized into particulates, organics, and inorganics, with different removal techniques for each:

- Particulates removal:** A modification membrane removes particles larger than 0.5 µm, primarily lunar dust. Smaller particles are not expected to reach the WPS.
- Organics removal:** Activated carbon (AC) is used, with steam regeneration considered to reduce consumables. Methanol, a critical organic contaminant, is expected to be mostly removed in the MECS, but if higher levels are detected, additional methods for total organic carbon (TOC) reduction will be explored.
- Inorganics removal:** Reverse osmosis (RO) is used for the efficient removal of inorganic materials, particularly ammonia, without consumables. RO concentrate is recirculated, minimizing wastewater generation. Ion exchange resin provides final polishing to meet purity requirements for technical water.

This approach ensures that the Water Purification Subsystem is both effective and efficient in preparing water for electrolysis while minimizing system waste and maintaining availability for future lunar applications.

"I do believe that our huge effort of finding water in places where it is hard to find brings extreme value to human logistic organization. It is also linked to how we decide to handle our footprint to human beings in the future."

Georg Bräuer, Fraunhofer IPT

LUWEX-LSG-WP6.1-D6.1-Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities-v1.0

WATER QUALITY AND CONDITION MONITORING SUBSYSTEM (WQCM)

The Water Quality and Monitoring Subsystem (WQCM) is designed for real-time monitoring of water quality in the system, positioned both upstream and downstream of the Water Purification Subsystem. It consists of two sensor arrays and a Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) system.

Sensor Arrays: Each sensor array includes a conductivity probe, a turbidity probe, and a pH sensor. The upstream array monitors the water before purification, while the downstream array monitors the water after purification. Conductivity probes measure ion concentration, turbidity probes assess suspended particles, and pH sensors verify conductivity readings and detect potential impurities during water production.

LIBS: The LIBS system uses a laser to create plasma from the water sample, which emits light that is analyzed to determine the composition. This allows for the detection of multiple pollutants without the need for numerous specific sensors, and it can be performed in-line without harming the water. The LIBS system uses a CNL-CPS-1064-S-300mJ laser, an Ocean FX DPX21102 spectrometer, and a custom measurement chamber to perform real-time analysis.

Additional Testing: In addition to the in-line monitoring, sample ports on the WPS allow water to be collected for laboratory testing, which provides higher accuracy for validating the in-line measurements and gaining additional insights.

This multilayered monitoring system ensures continuous, accurate assessment of water quality, detecting any anomalies in the purification process and supporting further analysis when needed.

LUWEX-LSG-WP6.1-D6.1-Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities-v1.0

"Water Quality means the presence or actually we are looking for the absence of specific ions, the specific chemical compounds that might be harmful for a crew, that is put out on the space."

Karel Lela, Wroclaw University of Science and Technology

LUWEX-LSG-WP6.1-D6.1-Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities-v1.0

Figure 27. System design and implementation section.

7.2.4 Project status

Figure 28. Project status section.

7.2.5 Results

Figure 29. Results section.

7.2.6 Adaptability to future missions

Figure 30. Adaptability to future missions section.

7.2.7 Water beyond Earth podcast

Figure 31. Podcast section.

8 D6.10: Project Video

The project video provided a comprehensive summary of the LUXEX project, outlining its goals and developments. Professionally recorded [see Figure 34], it featured lab footage and interviews with some of the team members offering personal insights into their contributions [see Figure 35]. It also provided project introduction and background and motivation [see Figure 36], an overview of the project partners [see Figure 37], and animations illustrating the mechanism behind the developed technology [see Figure 38].

The animations were instrumental in explaining the system's functionality and the interaction between its components to extract and purify lunar water. This process was shown in the context of its application for in-situ propellant and consumables production, supporting future space exploration missions.

The video concluded with credits listing all team members, acknowledging their contributions to the project's success [see Figure 39].

Figure 34. Video recording.

Figure 35. Screenshots from the video footage – Interviews with team members and system overview.

Figure 36. Screenshots from the summary video - Introduction, project background.

Figure 37. Screenshots from the summary video – Partner’s overview.

Figure 38. Screenshots from the summary video – Animation with a system overview.

Figure 39. Screenshots from the summary video – Credits.

9 Conference papers, fairs, poster presentations, exhibitions

9.1 Conferences

It is expected that consortium partners will attend international workshops and conferences to disseminate information on the project goals and achievements. LSG, with help from the other consortium partners will also prepare a public presentation and assure ad-hoc support to Horizon 2020 coordinators in its communication with the specialized press or scientific community on the outcomes of the project.

The team will prepare conference papers and articles, initiate presentations, and exhibitions to ensure effective and best possible impact of the project and its results. Feedback from conferences will be used to improve the work and to plan follow-up activities to increase the TRL of the LUWEX process and developed components.

Targeted international conferences include the International Astronautical Congress (IAC) because of its global nature and because it incorporates the world of science and business. In 2023 it will take place in Baku, Azerbaijan and in 2024 it will take place in Milan, Italy. The latter is favorable for the project since results can already be presented and normally European IACs are incredibly well visited. Another interesting scientific conference is the International Conference on Environmental Systems 2023 and in 2024. Further, the yearly Space Resource Week in Luxembourg and associated conferences at ESA are suitable to LUWEX outcomes to be presented in each project year.

As of now, the following conferences and workshops are on the LUWEX target list:

Table 9-1: List of target conferences and workshops

Conference/workshop name	Date	Location
International Astronautical Congress (IAC)	October 2023 October 2024 [annually]	Baku, Azerbaijan Milan, Italy
International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)	16-20 July 2023, July 2024 [annually]	Calgary, Canada
The Melissa Conference on regenerative life support systems for long term space missions	[annually]	
Space Resource Week	19-21 April 2023 [annually]	Luxembourg
Space Tech Expo Europe	14-16 November 2023	Bremen, Germany
Air and Space Academy (AAE) Conference	10-12 May 2023	Torino, Italy

The list of conferences here is just indicative, not exhaustive. More conferences will be added as the project progresses. DLR with assistance of LSG will track the participation of LUWEX consortium members at conferences for evaluation.

9.1.1 Space Resources Week 2023, Luxembourg

Space Resources Week 2023 gathered ~750 participants.

Figure 40. Space Resources Week 2023.

The LUWEX team members presented three posters [see Figure 41]:

- Review of Water Capturing, Devices for Lunar ISRU.
- Design Investigation of Lunar Water Extraction.
- Characterisation of Water contaminated by Lunar Regolith and Selection of n associated Water Purification System.

Figure 41. Posters presented at Space Resources Week 2023.

9.1.2 Space Resources Week 2024, Luxembourg

Figure 42. Space Resources Week 2024.

9.1.3 International Astronautical Congress 2023, Baku

International Astronautical Congress 2024 gathered >5.000 participants.

Figure 43. International Astronautical Congress 2023.

9.1.4 International Astronautical Congress 2024, Milan

International Astronautical Congress 2024 gathered ~11.000 participants. LUXWEX was presented at the Moon Exploration – Part 2 sessions, A3. IAF SPACE EXPLORATION SYMPOSIUM. This session addresses current and future lunar missions, orbital missions, robotic surface missions, as well as life sciences on the Moon, resource utilisation and preparatory activities for future solar system exploration.

Figure 44. International Astronautical Congress 2024.

Figure 45. Paul Zabel presenting LUWEX at International Astronautical Congress 2024.

9.1.5 Europlanet Science Congress EPSC2024

Europlanet Science Congress EPSC2024 gathered ~1.200 participants.

Figure 46. Europlanet Science Congress EPSC2024

9.1.6 Space Resources Roundtable

Space Resources Roundtable gathered 258 participants.

Figure 47. Space Resources Roundtable.

9.2 Stakeholder Workshops “Form the MOON to EARTH”

The online stakeholder workshop, titled “From the MOON to EARTH – How water technologies developed for the Moon can help our everyday life on Earth” took place on 18th June 2024.

The workshop was part of WP5.2 - Potential Terrestrial Applications Investigation, aiming to identify market potentials for transforming LUWEX-developed technologies into valuable applications. With participants invited for their potential commercial interests, the workshop contributes to the market scan analysis for possible terrestrial applications.

9.2.1 Workshop advertisement

The workshop was advertised on LUWEX website, and on LinkedIn [see Figure 48]. To advertise the workshop, there was an introductory video prepared, inviting for the workshop.

Figure 48. Screenshots of the LinkedIn post and workshop information on the LUWEX website

9.2.2 Workshop agenda

Below there is an agenda of the online workshop.

10:00 Welcome

- Introduction to LUWEX project (Paul Zabel, DLR) incl. Q+A
- Water purification & storage subsystem (Rachele Perelli, Thales Alenia Space) incl. Q+A
- Water monitoring subsystem (Karol Leluk, WUST) incl. Q+A

- Tour de table session (ca. 2-3 minutes per partner. Each of the partner prepares one slide concerning area of expertise/field of activity relating to their enterprise)

11:15 – 11:20 Break

- Introduction to possible terrestrial application. Report presentation (**Karol Leluk, WUST**)
- Open Discussion
 - how to potentially develop the technology itself further
 - introduction into the market: pros and cons, steps
 - summary

13:00 End of Workshop

9.2.3 Presentations

In the first part of the workshop, three presentations were given, each followed by a Q&A session.

9.2.3.a Introduction to LUXWEX project

Paul Zabel from DLR gave “Introduction to LUXWEX project” discussing context, project objectives, partners, expected outcomes and impacts, extraction and capturing process, experimental campaign, and dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan of the project [see Figure 49]. Paul Zabel also presented Workshop’s focus within the context of the project scope [see Figure 50].

During the Q&A session, a question was raised about the next steps for developing the system. The response highlighted the goal of making the system more comparable to space hardware, contingent on securing funding. It was noted that while the purification system is already akin to space hardware, the liquefaction system currently would not be suitable for use in space. Future design evolutions aim to address size, weight, and other specifications to better align with space hardware requirements.

Background: Water on the Moon

- Water on the lunar south pole:
 - Confirmed ± 5 wt.% in regolith in Cabeus crater (PSR) by LCROSS mission.
 - Micro cold traps (which are more accessible) believed to have 0,1 – 1 wt.% water in the regolith.
 - Indications of local patches containing up to 20 wt.% water in the regolith.
 - NASA's VIPER Mission will look for other water sources near (but not in) Nubite crater.
- Current gaps¹:
 - Form, concentration, and distribution of water is not known.
 - Technologies to locate and characterize resources.
 - Feasibility of mining techniques and operations in PSRs not verified by ground environmental chamber tests.

1: NASA - SRRP/Planetary & Terrestrial Mining Sciences Symposium (PTMSS) June 2021

Extraction and capturing process

- Design for extraction and water capturing chosen using simulations and trade-offs.
- A water extraction crucible and a cold trap capturing device are placed in a "dusty" TVAC.
 - Temperature $\approx 80 - 100$ K.
 - Pressure $\approx 10e-6$ mbar.
 - Crucible size = $\varnothing 30$ cm x 30 cm.
 - Icy regolith simulant mass up to 15 kg.
 - Amount of water present 5 wt.%, 750 mL (baseline)
 - Presence of volatiles: CO₂ & Methanol

Project schedule

Expected Outcomes and Impacts

Figure 49. Screenshots from the introduction presentation, by Paul Zabel

Figure 50. Project's scope and workshop's focus, Paul Zabel

9.2.3.b The Water purification & storage subsystem

Rachele Perelli from Thales Alenia Space presented “The Water purification & storage subsystem” outlining the Water purification & storage (WPS) overview, WPS design, and WPS test results [see Figure 51].

Figure 51. Screenshots from the presentation on Water Purification and Storage Subsystem by Rachele Perelli

During the Q&A session, a question was asked about the biggest challenge for implementation on the Moon. The response emphasized that the key challenges are developing technology suitable for the lunar surface, selecting appropriate materials, and effectively scaling the system up and down.

9.2.3.c Water monitoring subsystem

Karol Leluk from WUST presented “Water monitoring subsystem” [see Figure 52], discussing Water quality monitoring subsystem (WQMS) overview.

Figure 52. Screenshots from the presentation on water monitoring subsystem, by Karol Leluk, WUST

9.2.3.d Other aspects

Besides the technical aspects, the presentation discussed key players in the global water purification equipment market, SWOT Analysis, commercialization aspects and potential risks.

Key players in the global water purification equipment market:

- 3M Company
- Midea Group Co., Ltd.
- Culligan International Company
- Unilever PLC
- Coway Co., Ltd.
- O. Smith Corporation
- DuPont de Nemours, inc
- Kent RO Systems Ltd.
- Eureka Forbes Ltd
- Panasonic Corporation
- LG Corporation
- Pentair PLC
- BLUEWATER SWEDEN AB

SWOT Analysis

<p>STRENGTHS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Innovations for determining water quality, joining the trend of monitoring water for harmful substances. 2. Proven phenomena on which the technology is based. 3. Project consortium (scientific team). 4. The purpose of technology is to satisfy basic human needs. 	<p>WEAKNESSES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No IP protection strategy, no state of the Art. 2. No commercialization model. 3. Low TRL of the Technology. 4. Lack of information in the Project materials (eg. website) about other possible Technology uses on the Earth. 5. Made tests of Technology without the use of dirty earthly water.
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decreasing water resources - demand for such technology. 2. Market and social trends emphasizing this type of technologies as develop in LUWEX. 3. European Green Deal, Fit for 55 Package. 4. Using the LUWEX Project for advertising, marketing activities aimed at commercialization (obtaining a partner for further work on LUWEX technology). 	<p>THREATS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Competition of companies and another technologies. 2. Scaling (TRL increase) time and costs. 3. Long time commercialization and implementation process. 4. Possible patent infringements (third party rights).

Commercialization

It was noted that, there is no one universal water treatment system. In order to increase the chances of commercializing the technology, it is recommended:

1. Development of a technological offer and carrying out marketing activities.
2. Development of a patent protection and commercialization strategy.
3. Acquiring companies and potential end users of the technology.
4. Development of guidelines (technical, scientific) for a new implementation project based on Luwex Technology as and data from point 1 and 2 above background IP.
5. The pilot implementation. Performing a technological audit and developing guidelines (design assumptions, mass balances, heat balances, etc.) for pilot implementations. As a result will be received a functional and utility program and a feasibility study. The pilot implementation (successful) will contribute to the commercialization of the implementation of the Technology on the wide market

Risks

The discussed risks indicate that while the technological risk is low for technology implemented and tested on an industrial scale, the LUWEX Project is currently at TRL 4, meaning there is still a risk of not reaching TRL 9, which is crucial for successful implementation. Implementing R&D project results involves discount risks related to the level of technology and typical business risks. Estimating this discount risk is vital for valuing the technology, especially for selling or licensing it for commercialization. At low TRLs, technological discount risk is predominant, whereas mature technologies face primarily business risks in the market. Currently, the discount risk for the LUWEX technology is estimated at 30-40% due to its unproven status on a larger scale, despite the market being well understood. The technology represents a new product and manufacturing process in a known market, with no patent rights obstructing its implementation.

9.2.4 Tour de table

Following the introductory presentations, after the break, the next part of the workshop included Tour de table and introduction of guests.

Workshop participants [see Figure 53]:

- Karol Leluk, Anna Jurga, WUST, LUWEX team
- Paul Zabel, Mateo Rejon Lopes, DLR, LUWEX team
- Giorgio Boscheri, Rachele Perelli, Thomas Fili, TASI, LUWEX team
- Barbara Imhof, Monika Brandić Lipińska, LIQUIFER, LUWEX team

- Tomasz Marciniszyn, Tech-Transfer Company
- Marcin Kolonko, IMGW - The Institute of Meteorology and Water Management (weather forecast, prediction when water is available on earth)
- Katarzyna Martewicz, Department of Economy and Promotion, Marshal's office of the Lower Silesia
- Anna Kolonko-Wiercik, Wrocław's Municipal Water and Sewerage Company
- Giovanni Marchitelli, TASI
- Katarzyna Czepil, Wrocław Technology Transfer Centre, Horizon Contact Point
- Aleksandra Turyńska, Wrocław Technology Transfer Centre, Horizon Contact Point

- Brigitte Lamarze, ESA (water technologies, ISRU, water purification),
- Blandine Gorce, YGT in Life Support Systems, ESA (terrestrial applications, water treatment)

List of participants who were unable to take part in the workshop but reveal interest in LUWEX project progress:

- Maciej Sławiński, National Centre for Research and Development, Poland
- Hannah Sargeant, University of Leicester
- Ulrich Kuebler, Airbus
- Aude DeClerq, European Space Agency
- Małgorzata Hotyńska, Aude De Clercq, European Space Agency

Figure 53. Screenshots with workshop participants

9.2.5 Open Discussion

The focus of the open discussion was on the potential terrestrial applications of the water purification & water monitoring technologies developed with LUWEX project.

Unique selling points

During the stakeholder workshop, Brigitte Lamarze emphasized the need for a more detailed comparison between the LUWEX water purification technologies and current water purification systems. She pointed out that while the information provided was accurate, it lacked clarity on the specific advantages of LUWEX technologies over other purification systems. She stressed the importance of identifying and highlighting the unique selling points.

The discussion underscored the added value of LUWEX technologies and the need to thoroughly screen and analyze their specificities compared to existing solutions. Participants considered how these technologies could fit into various scenarios, such as integrating with existing water treatment plants or being implemented in new systems from scratch. The conversation acknowledged the potential for multiple systems to coexist and the necessity of advancing water recycling solutions.

Additionally, the workshop highlighted the importance of establishing specific use cases for LUWEX technologies. Attendees were asked for their thoughts on the potential of these technologies for terrestrial applications, aiming to gather diverse perspectives on their viability and advantages in different contexts.

Costs aspects

Marcin Kolonko raised a pertinent question about the cost of implementing the LUXWEX water purification system. In response, Karol Leluk acknowledged the difficulty in providing a precise cost estimate at this stage. He explained that the current production scale, which is geared towards space applications, results in higher costs due to small throughput and the need to address issues related to mass and size. These factors are less of a concern for terrestrial applications.

Karol Leluk highlighted that series production would significantly reduce the production costs, making the system more affordable per cubic meter of purified water. He emphasized the necessity of conducting a SWOT analysis to better understand the potential and feasibility of LUXWEX technologies for terrestrial applications. The initial implementation for demonstration purposes required relatively low material engineering efforts, but scaling up for widespread use would benefit from economies of scale.

Example of mountain facility

Karol Leluk shared an example of developing a water retention system for a mountain facility facing significant water issues. The mountain resort near Wroclaw experienced a high influx of tourists during hot summer days, leading to water shortages and the lack of toilet facilities on the mountain.

The initial solution involved transporting water containers by truck to provide water for handwashing and toilet use. However, the cost of building the necessary infrastructure was twice the value of the existing infrastructure. To address this, a more efficient system was proposed, which involved capturing rainfall, using a small filtering system, and producing greywater for handwashing and toilet use. This solution aimed to reduce costs and improve water management at the facility.

Potential in Lower Silesia

Participants also explored the practical applications of lunar-inspired water technologies in Lower Silesia. Anna Kolonko-Wiercik, representing municipal water treatment, highlighted the importance of continuous use for maintaining the functionality of water treatment technologies. This perspective underscores the need for sustainable and consistent implementation to ensure effective water treatment solutions in the region.

Karol expanded on this by discussing the potential for reclaiming valuable resources from wastewater, such as phosphate, nitrate, antibiotics, and pharmaceuticals. This approach not only addresses environmental concerns but also aligns with new European Commission wastewater directives aimed at reclaiming substances like hormones to enhance the overall effectiveness of wastewater treatment processes in Lower Silesia. These insights reflect a growing awareness and commitment to leveraging advanced water technologies developed for space missions to benefit everyday life on Earth, particularly in regions like Lower Silesia.

Water precipitation

Marcin Kolonko offered to connect Karol with contacts who could provide insights from Italy, Austria, and Germany, regarding their respective approaches to water management. This exchange highlights the workshop's collaborative spirit, aiming to gather diverse perspectives and expertise from across Europe.

One notable suggestion emerged regarding the LUXWEX system, which could be utilized for pre-cleaning and purifying wastewater effectively. Participants proposed leveraging precipitation maps and collaborating with colleagues across different countries to develop a comprehensive roadmap. This roadmap would analyze precipitation patterns in regions across Europe, particularly focusing on the four countries participating in LUXWEX. By pinpointing areas with both high and low water availability, stakeholders aim to demonstrate the system's potential benefits and feasibility in various environmental contexts.

Technology Readiness Levels

There was also discussion on advancing Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) and their practical applications. Giorgio Boscheri highlighted challenges in increasing TRL, emphasizing the transition from single prototypes in space to industrialization. The importance of testing environments—from labs to analog sites and eventually operational settings—was stressed for refining technologies and reducing costs and procurement times.

Participants queried Giorgio and Rachele on their experiences with TRL development. They noted that while TRLs traditionally relate to space, adapting them to terrestrial applications requires considerations like industrialization and testing in relevant environments. The analogy drawn to the EDEN ISS greenhouse, initially an analogue for space, later adapted for Antarctica, underscored the potential for technologies like LUXWEX to first be developed for remote or extreme environments before wider applications.

The discussion explored logistical parallels in remote areas and highlighted opportunities for synergy between space-developed TRLs and terrestrial solutions. This approach aims to identify common challenges and solutions across different environments, including deserts and other remote regions, thereby maximizing the utility of advanced technologies originally conceived for space missions.

Other applications

The workshop participants explored diverse applications beyond conventional uses of water technology. They discussed organizing a hackathon aimed at brainstorming innovative scenarios for technology application, emphasizing creativity over technical specifics. Military applications emerged as a key focus, with considerations for scenarios involving restricted water access during conflicts, highlighting the potential for water treatment tools to mitigate such challenges.

Participants considered unconventional applications such as soil purification and water extraction from polluted terrains. These discussions underscored the workshop's proactive approach to exploring novel uses of advanced water technologies, including their adaptation to environments like deserts and contaminated areas.

Moreover, the idea of engaging students through competitions was proposed to foster new perspectives and ideas. This approach not only encourages innovation but also integrates the enthusiasm and fresh thinking of younger generations into solving real-world water management issues.

9.2.6 Summary

The workshop highlighted key insights into applying lunar-inspired water technologies on Earth. Emphasis was placed on identifying unique advantages of LUXWEX purification systems, addressing cost efficiency through scaling, and exploring diverse applications in varied environments. Discussions on Technology Readiness Levels underscored the need for industrialization and practical testing, drawing parallels from space analogues. Recommendations included strategic steps for commercialization, such as patent protection and pilot implementations, aiming to enhance global water management solutions. Overall, the workshop fostered innovative thinking towards leveraging advanced technologies to meet pressing water challenges, echoing Marcin Kolonko's sentiment that "Water plays the role of gold" in modern society.

9.3 Trade fairs and exhibitions

Consortium partners attended international fairs to disseminate information about the project goals and achievements. DLR, with the assistance of LSG, tracked the participation of LUXWEX consortium members at these trade fairs to evaluate their impact and outreach effectiveness.

9.3.1 NEXT NATURE Space Farming: the food of tomorrow

On 24 September 2023, Next Nature launched its exhibition, *Spacefarming: The Food of Tomorrow* [see Figure 54]. This exhibition highlighted the ongoing food revolution both on Earth and in space, with LUXWEX featured as part of the showcase.

Figure 54. Space Farming Exhibition advertisement.

Spacefarming explored the immense potential of cultivating food in space and provided insights into how these innovations could transform life on Earth. The exhibition's design included geodesic domes housing a diverse range of ideas and innovations contributed by scientists, technologists, farmers, designers, philosophers, makers, and artists. Visitors were immersed in alternative culinary realities and introduced to the exciting possibilities of future food systems.

LUXWEX contributed to the exhibition with a poster detailing lunar regolith and regolith simulants. The display was enhanced by flasks containing regolith simulants and a fake regolith ice simulant to illustrate the presence of water in lunar regolith. The poster also explained the technology developed in the LUXWEX project, highlighting the water extraction and purification process for future lunar missions [see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** and Figure 56].

Figure 55. LUWEX poster in the making, for the NEXT NATURE Space Farming exhibition.

Figure 56. Arrangement of the LUWEX project exhibited at the NEXT NATURE Space Farming exhibition.

10 Summary

The Dissemination Report outlines the outreach and dissemination activities undertaken during the LUWEX project. Throughout the project, consortium partners utilised a range of methods and tools to achieve the dissemination objectives. The LUWEX team also established synergies with other EU-funded projects, enhancing the impact and reach of the project outcomes.

Consortium partners contributed information from their respective parts of the project to foster public engagement and awareness. These efforts successfully inspired and educated the target audience on the possibilities and techniques for extracting and refining water on the Moon, a critical resource for producing fuel and other supplies required for future human space missions. These activities have supported progress towards a more sustainable future for space exploration.